

Effect of the stage of introducing a cross-linking agent on the structure and physicochemical properties of the graft copolymer of xanthan with acrylamide - perspective sorption membrane material

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Supplementary Materials

Table S1. Quantitative characteristics of the synthesis process of graft copolymer XG-g-PAAm

Sample No. XG-g-PAAm	Volume of AAm solution, ml	Mass ratio $m_{\text{XG}}:m_{\text{AAm}}$	MBA introduction stage
1			t_i
2	2	0.12:0.8	t_p
3			t_f
4			t_i
5	4	0.12:1.6	t_p
6			t_f
7			t_i
8	8	0.12:3.2	t_p
9			t_f

Fig. S1. FTIR spectra of the XG-g-PAAm-1 (-2, -3, -7, -8, -9) copolymer samples. The dotted lines highlight the vibration ranges of the main characteristic signals: 1 – $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$, $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$; 2 – $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$, $\delta_{\text{C-H}}$; 3 – $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$, $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$; 4 – $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, $\delta_{\text{C-H}}$; 5 – $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-C}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$.

Figure S2-1. X-ray diffraction patterns of xanthan gum and XG-g-PAAm-1 (-2, -3) samples obtained at a mass ratio of mXG:mAAM 0.12:0.8. The amorphous halo is indicated by the purple lines.

Fig. S2-2. X-ray diffraction patterns of xanthan gum and XG-g-PAAm-7 (-8, -9) samples obtained at a mass ratio of mXG:mAAM 0.12:3.2. The amorphous halo is indicated by the purple lines.

(a)

(b)

Fig. S3. Sorption kinetics of liquid water and H₂O vapor (marked with a prime) by XG-g-PAAm-1 (-4, -7) graft copolymer samples obtained by introducing the cross-linking agent at the chain termination stage (t_i) (a), by XG-g-PAAm-2 (-5, -8) graft copolymer samples obtained by introducing the cross-linking agent at the chain termination stage (t_p) (b).

Fig. S4. Kinetics of methylene blue sorption by XG-g-PAAm-1 (-4, -7) graft copolymer samples obtained by introducing the crosslinking agent at the stage of chain termination (t_i) (a), by XG-g-PAAm-3 (-6, -9) graft copolymer samples obtained by introducing the crosslinking agent at the stage of chain termination (t_f) (b) in standard coordinates

Fig. S5-1. Kinetics of methylene blue sorption by XG-g-PAAm-1 (-4, -7) graft copolymer samples obtained by introducing the crosslinking agent at the stage of chain termination (t_i) in coordinates of pseudo-first (a) and pseudo-second order (b) models, the combined model (c) and the pseudo- n^{th} order model (d) with theoretical Q_e values (lines).

Fig. S5-2. Kinetics of methylene blue sorption by XG-g-PAAm-3 (-6, -9) graft copolymer samples obtained by introducing the crosslinking agent at the stage of chain termination (t_f) in coordinates of pseudo-first (a) and pseudo-second order (b) models, the combined model (c) and the pseudo- n^{th} order model (d) with theoretical Q_e values (lines).

Fig. S6. Kinetics of methylene blue sorption by XG-g-PAAm-1 (-4, -7) graft copolymer samples obtained by introducing the crosslinking agent at the stage of chain termination (t_i) (a) and by XG-g-PAAm-3 (-6, -9) graft copolymer samples obtained by introducing the crosslinking agent at the stage of chain termination (t_f) (b) in the coordinates of intraparticle diffusion.

Table S2. The significance of linear regression coefficients of the kinetics of the sorption of methylene blue by XG-g-PAAm samples in the coordinates of kinetic models

Sample No. XG-g-PAAm	$y=(b\pm\Delta b)x + (a\pm\Delta a)$	
	Pseudo-first order	Pseudo-second order
1	$(-0.006\pm 0.00064)x + (0.3013\pm 0.17930)$	$(0.6818\pm 0.05)x + (93.233\pm 27.00)$
2	$(-0.006\pm 0.0013)x + (0.167\pm 0.3674)$	$(0.5576\pm 0.01)x + (34.273\pm 10.47)$
3	$(-0.0087\pm 0.00051)x + (-0.712\pm 0.15396)$	$(0.809\pm 0.02)x + (24.258\pm 4.65)$
4	$(-0.0069\pm 0.0011)x + (0.2193\pm 0.3056)$	$(0.6192\pm 0.0179)x + (38.287\pm 12.8673)$
5	$(-0.0081\pm 0.0011)x - (0.035\pm 0.3044)$	$(0.62\pm 0.0074)x + (19.626\pm 6.5285)$
6	$(-0.0077\pm 0.0011)x - (0.0681\pm 0.2463)$	$(0.8488\pm 0.1556)x + (174.54\pm 43.5719)$
7	$(-0.0038\pm 0.0081)x - (0.2905\pm 2.2625)$	$(0.8096\pm 0.0228)x + (66.543\pm 16.4167)$
8	$(-0.0041\pm 0.0004)x - (0.0013\pm 0.1097)$	$(0.7791\pm 0.0161)x + (99.701\pm 14.2984)$
9	$(-0.0102\pm 0.0014)x - (0.1722\pm 0.2994)$	$(1.2432\pm 0.1830)x + (250.8\pm 45.84)$